

An Adaptive Physics-informed Deep Operator Neural Network for 1-D Unsaturated Infiltration Model Coupled with Soil Deformation

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Abstract: The advent of deep learning has opened up a new avenue for studying groundwater flow dynamics in unsaturated soils. Among these, physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) can achieve PDEs forward inference and parameter inversion with a limited amount of data. However, they require retraining when the initial conditions, boundary conditions and equation coefficients are different, which restricts their applicability in the rapid prediction of geotechnical responses. In neural networks, the weights can be adjusted to rectify the constructed loss function, thereby influencing the computational accuracy. In this paper, we propose a physics-informed deep operator learning network with adaptive loss weights (a-PIDeepONet) to solve a one-dimensional (1-D) unsaturated infiltration model coupled with soil deformation. The efficacy of a-PIDeepONet for expeditious prediction of groundwater seepage in unsaturated soils is evaluated under diverse initial conditions. The a-PIDeepONet is trained on a training dataset comprising initial conditions, after which it is tested on a test dataset comprising different initial conditions. On this basis, the influence of the network structure and the weight of the loss function on the computational accuracy is analysed. The results show that the proposed a-PIDeepONet achieves good results in unsaturated infiltration problems. This study provides an effective tool for modelling unsaturated infiltration and shows potential for constructing large AI models for fast prediction of geotechnical responses.

Keywords: Physics-informed DeepONet; Adaptive Loss Weights Balance; Groundwater Flow, Unsaturated Infiltration; Geotechnical Response; Fast Prediction

1. Introduction

Geotechnical engineering frequently grapples with intricate nonlinear relationships, necessitating the solution of partial differential equations (PDEs). Traditionally, methods such as the Finite Difference Method (FDM), Finite Volume Method (FVM), and Finite Element Method (FEM) have been employed to tackle these PDEs (1-4). Recently, physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) have emerged as a groundbreaking alternative (5). By embedding the residuals of PDEs into the loss function during model training, PINNs optimise this function through deep learning techniques, allowing for approximating a diverse array of PDEs while maintaining computational accuracy and irrelevance of step size (6). Unlike conventional numerical methods, which rely on discretisation or interpolation in time-domain computations, PINNs offer a more flexible solution process and outcomes. Moreover, the PINNs framework can tackle inverse problems associated with PDEs, enabling the extraction of governing equations or parameters from realistic data (7, 8). Nonetheless, it is important to note that traditional methods and PINNs are often limited to solving specific problems and necessitating prolonged training. Changes in problem conditions can lead to the need for recomputation, which significantly hampers computational efficiency and generalisation of such models. In response to these limitations, operator learning has introduced a more universal solution paradigm (9). This approach focuses on learning mappings between function spaces, enabling well-trained neural operators to predict PDE solutions accurately, even when input conditions change (10). Among the prominent contributions to neural operators is DeepONet because of its innovative capabilities and superior performance (11). Notably, the physics-informed DeepONet circumvents the necessity for data-driven training, as it only learns from PDEs that encapsulate physical laws (12). In the training process of neural operators, the influence of each loss term on final predictions cannot be underestimated. To this end, we propose the adaptive Physics-informed Deep Operator Neural Network (a-PIDeepONet), which emphasises the loss-weight balancing to enhance predictive performance further.

Therefore, to explore the applicability of this novel algorithm within geotechnical engineering, this paper focuses on a 1-D unsaturated infiltration model that is coupled with soil deformation. By leveraging the a-PIDeepONet algorithm, we conduct a thorough examination of the solution process and validate the model by comparing it against reference solutions. The effectiveness of this method is established through a comparative analysis between the reference solutions and the outcomes generated by the a-PIDeepONet algorithm, demonstrating its feasibility for addressing unsaturated infiltration challenges in the field of geotechnical engineering.

2. Methodology

This section outlines the fundamental methodology of the paper, detailing the algorithmic structure employed in this research, the physical governing equations relevant to the research problem, and the construction and optimization of the loss function.

2.1 The architecture of adaptive physics-informed deep operator neural network

The adaptive Physics-informed Deep Operator Neural Network (a-PIDeepONet) is a neural network-based neural operator model that mainly learns mappings between function spaces and can be used for unsupervised learning tasks. It learns the governing equations that imply the underlying physical laws and predicts the dynamical behaviour of physical systems with little or no data. Unlike traditional neural networks or PINNs, a-PIDeepONet contains two layers of neural networks, a trunk network and a branch network, where the inputs to the trunk network are spatiotemporal coordinates, and the branch network receives the family of input functions mapped to the solution of the PDEs. Finally, the outputs of the two networks are interlinked together by a dot-product operation, which brings the final outputs of the a-PIDeepONet. In addition, a-PIDeepONet incorporates the residuals of the PDEs that control the underlying physical laws into the loss function as constraints. This approach effectively enhances the model's ability to identify physical problems and improves the accuracy and robustness of numerical simulations. Furthermore, the model's generalisation is also greatly improved as the model learns mappings between families of functions. By combining the loss function of the physics equations with that of the neural network, it is possible to improve the satisfaction of the physics equations by optimising the loss function during training, ensuring that the final results conform to the specific physics laws.

The main idea of a-PIDeepONet is to embed PDEs as constraints into the training process of the neural network using automatic differentiation with loss-based adaptive weight balancing, thus enabling unsupervised learning (without any additional training data) and the solution of PDEs. The structure of a-PIDeepONet is shown in the following figure for reference. (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 The architecture of the adaptive physics-informed deep operator neural network (a-PIDeepONet).

The a-PIDeepONet model, as illustrated in the figure, comprises two types of networks. a represents the family of input functions and is processed through the branch layers, while the coordinates (z, t) corresponding to the spatiotemporal data are processed through the trunk layers. The network consists of 7 hidden layers (indicated by $n = 7$), with the activation function being $\sigma = \tanh$. Specifically, each hidden layer in the neural network contains 100 neurons in this study. The neural network employed in a-PIDeepONet is the modified multilayer perceptron (MLP). For Vanilla MLP, the principle for a single layer can be expressed as $u = \sigma(W \cdot \sigma(x) + b)$, where x is the input and W, b are the weight and bias of the network. For modified MLP, the principle adopts three different sets of weights and biases, which is shown below:

$$u = \sigma\{\sigma(Wx + b) * [\sigma(W_1x + b_1)] + [1 - \sigma(Wx + b)] * [\sigma(W_2x + b_2)]\} \quad (1)$$

The outputs from the branch and trunk layers are combined using a dot product to figure out the final outputs of a-PIDeepONet, and $G_\theta(\mathbf{u})(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{t})$ indicates the learned operator of the PDE solution. In a-PIDeepONet, the loss function measures the difference between the model's output values and the exact physics. This model can simultaneously address initial conditions, boundary conditions, and PDEs of a physical field. Accordingly, the loss function typically consists of three components. The first component is the initial condition loss, which quantifies the prediction error by measuring the difference between the predicted and the actual initial

conditions of a physical problem. The second component is the boundary condition loss, which also reflects a prediction error—it captures the difference between the predicted results and the actual values at the physical problem's boundaries. The third component is the PDE residual loss, which represents the physical constraint error, measuring the discrepancy between the model's predictions and the governing equations across the entire physical domain. The total loss function is essentially the weighted sum of the initial condition loss, boundary condition loss, and PDE residual loss. An optimisation algorithm, such as gradient descent, is used to minimise the total loss. This algorithm iteratively adjusts the model's weights and biases until the goal of loss minimisation is achieved.

Finally, three loss terms can be computed using mean square error (MSE), corresponding to the initial conditions, boundary conditions, and the residuals of the PDEs, denoted as $\mathcal{J}[\mathbf{G}_\theta(\mathbf{u})]_\Omega(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{0})$, $\mathcal{B}[\mathbf{G}_\theta(\mathbf{u})]_{\partial\Omega}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{t})$, and $\mathcal{N}[\mathbf{G}_\theta(\mathbf{u})]_\Omega(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{t})$, respectively. Each loss term is assigned a corresponding weight based on themselves, and these weights are used to form a total loss function. This total loss function is minimised through optimisation, enabling the model to effectively learn the specific PDEs.

2.2 Neural operator based on physical information

The key to the neural operator's implementation of the mapping between function spaces is to include the residuals of the partial differential equations that control the physics as a part of the loss function. The objective of this study is to obtain mappings from different initial conditions to the solution of the PDE. With a well-trained neural operator model, we can quickly predict the PDE solution by inputting any initial conditions, which are often generated by Gaussian Random Field (GRF). GRF generates initial conditions based on physical priors and the need for numerical stability: 1. Physical Plausibility: GRF should encompass a range of initial states that PDEs may encounter, ensuring diverse training data. 2. Computational Feasibility: Appropriate parameters must be selected to avoid overly complex or unstable initial conditions. 3. Generalisation Ability: The parameters of GRF should guarantee that the training data is sufficiently rich, enabling the model to be robust against varying initial conditions. In addition, the GRF parameter setting has a significant impact on the accuracy and generalisation of model predictions. From numerical experience, if the mean shift is large, it may lead to an increase in model error. If the variance or the high-frequency component is increased, the model may be difficult to generalise from high-frequency or large-amplitude initial conditions, affecting the prediction accuracy. Therefore, introducing appropriate GRF parameters during training to generate physically consistent and stable samples can effectively improve the robustness and generalisation ability of the model. To further validate the effectiveness of the a-PIDeepONet, we aim to measure the accuracy and efficiency of the model by comparing the predictions with reference solutions. This reference solution is generated in MATLAB using high-order accuracy finite difference methods (FDM). Moreover, training on the GPU significantly enhances computational efficiency due to its parallel computing capabilities. In this study, the a-PIDeepONet is trained on a GPU equipped with an NVIDIA Tesla T4 GPU card with 16 GB of memory. A classical physics problem in geotechnical engineering is considered in this study: 1-D unsaturated infiltration model coupled with soil deformation. Wu et al. (2016)(13) assumed that the elastic modulus of the partially saturated soil is independent of soil suction, and the resulting model can be expressed as the following governing equation:

$$M_s e^{\alpha\psi} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t} - \alpha K(\psi) \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[K(\psi) \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial z} \right] = 0 \quad (2)$$

$K(\psi)$ represents the hydraulic conductivity related to the pressure head ψ . Specifically, Zhu et al. (2022)(14) reformulated this model, and we consider different initial conditions and a specific type of periodic boundary conditions in this model as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{M_s}{\alpha} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} - K_s \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} - \frac{K_s}{\alpha} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} = 0, z, t \in [0, 1] \\ u(z, 0) = u_0(z), z \in [0, 1] \\ u(0, t) = u(L, t), u_z(0, t) = u_z(L, t), L = 1, t \in [0, 1] \\ u = e^{\alpha\psi} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Where $u = e^{\alpha\psi}$ is the Kirchhoff variable, and ψ is the pressure head to be solved. $\alpha = 0.1m^{-1}$ is the fitting parameter that is related to the pore-size distribution. $M_s = \theta_s \alpha + \gamma_w / F$ and $\theta_s = 0.5$ is the saturated water content, $\gamma_w = 10kN/m^3$ represents the unit weight of water, $F = -2000kPa$ indicates the elastic modulus of the partially saturated soil ascertained by the total stress, and the soil is collapsible when the value is negative. $K_s = 1 \times 10^{-3}m/his$ the saturated hydraulic conductivity. The soil thickness is $L = 1m$ and the total evolutionary time is set to $t = 1h$.

The initial conditions, boundary conditions, and PDE residuals of the physical model being studied are outlined in Equation (3). These elements are used to construct the loss function of the a-PIDeepONet. To figure out the mapping from the initial conditions to the PDE solution, 80 different initial conditions are used as the training dataset, while another 20 unique initial conditions serve as the test dataset.

2.3 Loss function and training

The loss function considers the initial conditions, boundary conditions, and residuals of the PDEs.

$$Loss = \omega_{ic} \cdot Loss_{ic} + \omega_{bc} \cdot Loss_{bc} + \omega_{pde} \cdot Loss_{pde} \quad (4)$$

The $Loss_{ic}$ in Equation (4) corresponds to the initial condition, which represents the initial distribution of the pressure head at $t = 0$. $Loss_{bc}$ corresponds to the boundary condition covering the values of the pressure head when $z = 0$ and $z = L$. As mentioned earlier, periodic boundary conditions are used in this study. $Loss_{pde}$ represents the losses of the PDE residuals, i.e., the governing equations that are guaranteed to satisfy the physical laws. ω_{ic} , ω_{bc} and ω_{pde} represent the weights of the three loss terms, respectively. Specifically, according to the physical model of the 1-D unsaturated infiltration model coupled with soil deformation, the initial condition loss can be defined as follows based on the MSE loss:

$$Loss_{ic} = \frac{1}{N_{ic}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{ic}} (|\hat{u}_0 - u_0|^2) \quad (5)$$

Where \hat{u} and u in the equation indicate the predicted and the reference value respectively. In addition, the boundary condition loss is shown below according to the definition of periodic boundary:

$$Loss_{bc} = \frac{1}{N_{bc}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{bc}} (|\hat{u}(0, t) - \hat{u}(L, t)|^2 + \left| \frac{\partial \hat{u}(0, t)}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial \hat{u}(L, t)}{\partial z} \right|^2) \quad (6)$$

Similarly, we can define the PDE loss based on the residuals of the governing equation:

$$Loss_{pde} = \frac{1}{N_{pde}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{pde}} \left(\left| \frac{M_s}{\alpha} \frac{\partial \hat{u}}{\partial t} - K_s \frac{\partial \hat{u}}{\partial z} - \frac{K_s}{\alpha} \frac{\partial^2 \hat{u}}{\partial z^2} \right|^2 \right) \quad (7)$$

In these equations, N_{ic} , N_{bc} , and N_{pde} denote the number of points to be evaluated from the initial condition, the boundary condition, and the governing PDE in the computational domain, respectively. Furthermore, each loss term achieves adaptive weight balancing based on optimisation during training. Therefore, the balanced loss weights are considered as follows:

$$\omega_i = \frac{e^{|Loss_i|}}{e^{\sum |Loss_i|}}, i = ic, bc, pde \quad (8)$$

The prediction accuracy of a-PIDeepONet is evaluated in a well-trained model. The relative L_2 error is defined as:

$$Relative L_2 Error = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \|\hat{u} - u\|_{L_2}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \|u\|_{L_2}} \quad (9)$$

Where n is the number of spatiotemporal points in the whole domain. In a-PIDeepONet, the number of sensors for input samples (initial conditions in this study) is $m = 101$. In addition, the numbers of locations for each input sample for evaluating the initial condition, boundary condition and PDE residual are $P_{ic} = 101$, $P_{bc} = 100$, and $P_{pde} = 2500$, respectively. Meanwhile, the resolution of the uniform grid for the testing data is $P_{test} = 101$. After constructing the loss function, an Adam optimiser with an initial learning rate of 0.001 is used to update the parameters of a-PIDeepONet and minimise the loss function. The number of total training epoch is 60000 with a batch size of 2000. Finally, Figure 2 presents the workflow of a-PIDeepONet.

Figure 2 The flowchart of the general modelling strategy including training/testing scheme of the a-PIDeepONet.

3. Numerical results

The experimental results of the 1-D unsaturated infiltration model coupled with soil deformation are shown in Figure 3. Firstly, a-PIDeepONet is trained on a dataset with 80 different initial conditions. Then, it predicts results on 20 different initial conditions. Finally, we select 5 different initial conditions from the testing dataset with 20 different initial conditions to present the results of the pressure head ψ eventually predicted by a-PIDeepONet, the reference solutions, and the distributions of the error between the predictions and the reference solutions.

Figure 3 The comparison of the pressure head ψ between reference solution and prediction, and error plots illustrating 5 representative initial conditions among the 20 testing samples.

From the numerical results, it can be analysed that the well-trained a-PIDeepONet can quickly and accurately predict the solution of the PDE for arbitrarily different inputs of initial conditions, which is a strong advantage of neural operator learning over traditional numerical methods and PINNs. Meanwhile, a-PIDeepONet predicts the final pressure head ψ evolved from different initial conditions, and they agree well with the reference solution. In particular, the relative L_2 error of the predictions of the proposed model is at a low level with a range of

$$2.1e - 3 \sim 2.4e - 3,$$

i.e., the accuracy of the predictions is in the range of 99.7% – 99.8%. Also, we can observe from the error plots that the errors in the a-PIDeepONet predictions are mainly concentrated in the period of 0.2h after the start of the initial conditions, which provides a research direction for the development of more advanced unsupervised physics-informed neural operator models in the future. Moreover, besides initial conditions, a-PIDeepONet has more potential for generalisation by learning mappings from different equation parameters, boundary conditions, and external forcing source terms to the PDE solutions, which offers hope for a large AI model for computational mechanics in geotechnical engineering. In addition, we also show below the loss history plot of the training process of a-PIDeepONet, which reveals the operator learning process of a-PIDeepONet.

Figure 4 The loss function history during a-PIDeepONet training.

The loss history graph illustrates our proposed adaptive weight balancing approach. By monitoring the optimisation process of different loss terms promptly, a-PIDeepONet can self-update the weight assigned to each loss term. This adjustment is made with a focus on the global optimal path, allowing the model to search for the optimal path and solution of the loss function using the Adam optimiser. As a result, the model ultimately achieves the desired level of prediction accuracy and generalisation. To assess the generalisation robustness of our model's predictions, we conduct multiple independent runs, and the results are displayed in Table 1 below.

Table 1 Relative L_2 Errors of different initial conditions.

Trial	Train: Test	Kirchhoff Variable		Pressure Head		Model Average
		PINN	a-PIDeepONet	PINN	a-PIDeepONet	
1	80: 20	$1.26e-3$	$1.12e-3$	$1.39e-2$	$9.00e-3$	$2.35e-3$
2	80: 20	$2.72e-3$	$9.73e-4$	$1.67e-2$	$7.31e-3$	$2.31e-3$
3	80: 20	$2.58e-3$	$1.16e-3$	$1.20e-2$	$8.77e-3$	$2.26e-3$
4	80: 20	$4.26e-3$	$2.38e-3$	$1.18e-2$	$8.28e-3$	$2.17e-3$
5	80: 20	$1.81e-3$	$5.75e-4$	$9.44e-3$	$9.07e-3$	$2.12e-3$

In Table 1, there are five sets of independently repeated experiments. In each run, 'Train: Test' indicates that there are 80 initial conditions in the training set and 20 in the test set. The table displays the results of Kirchhoff Variable and Pressure Head, as the model first outputs Kirchhoff Variable before generating Pressure Head based on the physical control equations. 'Model Average' represents the average error in Kirchhoff Variable for a-PIDeepONet over the 20 test initial conditions in each run. Based on the numerical analysis above, the proposed a-PIDeepONet demonstrates robust performance in surrogate modelling for predicting unsaturated infiltration problems in geotechnical engineering. It can consistently and accurately predict key variables, including the Kirchhoff variable u and pressure head ψ of the problem. Additionally, a-PIDeepONet can quickly compute solutions for 20 different initial conditions in less than one second, while traditional numerical methods, which rely on cyclic calculations, often take several minutes. Therefore, the results greatly highlight the effectiveness and potential of a-PIDeepONet for similar problems in geotechnical engineering.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, we utilise a-PIDeepONet to solve a classical problem in geotechnical engineering — 1-D unsaturated infiltration model coupled with soil deformation. During the experiment, the balance of the loss function is adaptively adjusted based on real-time values of each term, enhancing the model's stability and robustness. We compare the results of our method with those of the reference solution, achieving accuracies that exceed 99% across the board. Moreover, a-PIDeepONet can simultaneously predict from multiple input functions with good performance, which surpasses traditional numerical methods and PINNs. This study provides an effective tool for unsaturated infiltration modelling and shows the potential for building large-scale artificial intelligence models to rapidly predict geotechnical responses.

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